

Coexistence of Smooth Muscle Tumor of Uncertain Malignant Potential (STUMP), Symplastic Leiomyoma, and Squamous Cell Carcinoma in Situ in a Nulliparous Patient: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Smooth muscle tumors of uncertain malignant potential (STUMPs) constitute a rare and diagnostically challenging subset of uterine mesenchymal neoplasms. Their clinical behavior is unpredictable, and preoperative distinction from benign leiomyomas or leiomyosarcomas remains difficult. Coexistence with cervical squamous neoplasia is exceedingly uncommon and sparsely documented.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 36-year-old nulliparous woman with a 12-year history of symptomatic uterine leiomyomatosis who presented with severe abnormal uterine bleeding and life-threatening anemia. Imaging over the years demonstrated progressively enlarging uterine masses, including a large pedunculated lesion occupying the entire pelvis. Emergency total hysterectomy was performed due to hemodynamic instability. Gross examination revealed three distinct tumors: a large transcervical polypoid mass, a bilobulated subserosal tumor and an intramural leiomyoma. Histopathological evaluation demonstrated a colliding tumor composed of a transcervical symplastic leiomyoma associated with cervical squamous intraepithelial neoplasia with foci of early stromal invasion, and a subserosal STUMP characterized by focal necrosis and cytologic atypia but low mitotic activity. The postoperative course was favorable, and the patient was referred to gynecologic oncology for long-term surveillance.

Discussion: This case is notable for the unusual coexistence of a STUMP, a symplastic leiomyoma, and cervical squamous neoplasia with microinvasion in a patient significantly younger than the typical age reported for STUMPs. The case highlights the diagnostic difficulty, unpredictable biological behavior, and lack of standardized management or follow-up guidelines for STUMP, emphasizing the importance of individualized treatment and monitoring due to recurrence risk.

Conclusion: Uterine STUMPs remain a management challenge given their uncertain malignant potential, radiologic ambiguity, and absence of clear follow-up recommendations. This case

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underscores the necessity for personalized surveillance strategies, particularly when multiple synchronous uterine neoplasms are present.

KEYWORDS: Uterine smooth muscle tumor of uncertain malignant potential (STUMP), symplastic leiomyoma, cervical squamous intraepithelial neoplasia, microinvasive cervical carcinoma, uterine leiomyomatosis, colliding uterine tumors, long-term oncologic surveillance, case report.

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INTRODUCTION

Uterine smooth muscle tumors are the most common mesenchymal tumors of the female urogenital system. The World Health Organization classifies these tumors into leiomyomas, smooth muscle tumors of uncertain malignant potential (STUMP), and leiomyosarcomas. (1) Under this classification, a STUMP is defined as a tumor that cannot be unequivocally diagnosed as benign or malignant. Despite their relatively low malignant potential, cases of recurrence and metastasis have been reported. (2)

STUMPs tend to affect perimenopausal or postmenopausal women, typically between 45 and 55 years of age at the time of diagnosis. They represent approximately 2–5% of all uterine smooth muscle tumors. (3) The estimated 5-year survival rate ranges from 92% to 100%. (4)

The term STUMP first appeared in 1973. (5) Several factors contribute to the difficulty in classifying these tumors, as they exhibit histological features that overlap with those of clearly benign and malignant smooth muscle tumors, including mild nuclear atypia, low mitotic indices, and focal necrosis. (6)

They do not present with specific clinical symptoms, instead sharing the typical manifestations of leiomyomas such as abnormal uterine bleeding, anemia, fatigue, rapid tumor growth, and pelvic pain. Currently, no recognized radiologic or biochemical markers exist for their diagnosis, nor are there established guidelines for their management. (7)

CLINICAL CASE

A 36-year-old Mexican nulliparous woman, weighing 45 kg and measuring 147 cm in height, with no chronic degenerative diseases or allergies, and a history of dilation and curettage 6 years prior secondary to incomplete miscarriage. She had intermittently attended gynecology hospital services with a diagnosis of abnormal uterine bleeding secondary to uterine leiomyomatosis of 12 years' progression. She had no history of cervical cytological screening and had required multiple hospital admissions, during which several CT scans were performed.

Twelve years earlier, an abdominopelvic CT scan with intravenous contrast revealed an enlarged uterus measuring

100 × 160 mm, lobulated, containing four hypodense images with heterogeneous contrast enhancement: two on the right (45 mm and 40 mm in diameter) and two on the left, each measuring 7 cm, rounded, one protruding into the endometrial cavity. Both ovaries showed normal echogenicity and size.

Five years earlier, a new non-contrast abdominopelvic CT showed a retroverted uterus with loss of its usual morphology, enlarged to approximately 126 × 80 × 70 mm, lobulated contours, and heterogeneous myometrium secondary to multiple heterogeneous predominantly hypoechoic nodular images compatible with fibroids. One intramural lesion measured 90 × 84 mm, located on the anterior wall at the body and fundus. At least four subserosal fibroids were observed arising from the uterine fundus: the largest was subhepatic and measured 14 × 10 cm; two others measured 7 × 5 cm in the midline infraumbilical area; and another measured 9 × 8 cm in the left iliac fossa. The right ovary measured 43 × 41 × 31 mm (≈28 cm³), containing a simple cyst of 32 mm with thin, smooth walls and anechoic content. The left ovary measured 39 × 35 × 24 mm (≈17.9 cm³), preserving its follicular pattern and containing a prominent 19 × 17 mm follicle.

One year earlier, another non-contrast abdominopelvic CT again reported a pedunculated fibroid occupying the entire pelvic cavity, measuring 244 × 132 mm, and a cystic structure overlying the main lesion, measuring 59 mm, likely corresponding to the left ovary.

Upon the current hospital admission, the patient presented with severe anemia (hemoglobin 3.7 g/dL), one month of abnormal uterine bleeding, and a cervical mass suspicious for malignancy. A punch biopsy of the lesion was performed, which reported: stroma with severe acute inflammation, granulation tissue, and clusters of coccoid bacteria. Histologic sections showed cervical stroma with total erosion of the exocervical and endocervical epithelium, reactive proliferation of fibroblasts and capillaries, abundant acute inflammatory infiltrate (polymorphonuclear cells), and surface fibrin deposits, necrosis, and clusters of coccoid bacteria (Figures 1–2). No squamous or endocervical epithelium and no malignant neoplasm were identified.

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Figure 1–2. Histological sections of cervical biopsies. Complete erosion of the epithelium is observed, with reactive proliferation of fibroblasts and capillary vessels, as well as acute inflammatory infiltrate.

The patient was stabilized with blood transfusions and prepared for surgery; however, during hospitalization she developed massive uterine bleeding requiring vasopressor support. An emergency hysterectomy was performed. Three large tumor masses were found, with a total specimen length (uterus + tumors) of 30 cm and a total weight of 1790 g. A small amount of free intraperitoneal fluid was noted, and intraoperative blood loss was 1200 mL.

The surgical specimen was submitted for histopathological analysis. It weighed 1790 g; the uterine body was ovoid, measuring 16 × 12 × 10 cm, with a light brown, smooth, opaque surface. Three nodular lesions were identified macroscopically (Figure 3).

The first lesion was polypoid and pedunculated, protruding through the cervical canal and os, measuring 10 × 9 × 6 cm. It was dark brown, with anfractuous inferior surface and areas of surface necrosis. On cut section, it appeared solid, brown, and fleshy.

The second lesion was subserosal, arising from the uterine fundus, bilobed, with lobes measuring 13 × 11 × 7 cm and 6 × 5 × 3.5 cm. The smaller lobe showed cystic degeneration, whereas the larger was solid, brown, and fleshy (Figure 4).

The third lesion was intramural, measuring 9 × 7.5 × 7 cm, solid, white, well-circumscribed, with a whorled appearance (Figures 5–6).

Figure 3–4. Surgical specimen at the time of extraction in the operating room, showing the three previously described nodular lesions.

Figure 5–6. Sagittal section of the surgical specimen.

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Histologic sections from the exocervix revealed a cervical intraepithelial lesion occupying the full epithelial thickness, characterized by abnormal maturation, nuclear enlargement, loss of cellular polarity, altered nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio, nuclear contour irregularity, hyperchromasia, and atypical mitoses. No invasive areas were identified in the cervical sections.

Histologic sections of the transcervical lesion showed a mesenchymal neoplasm with an ulcerated surface, partly covered by high-grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia

(Figures 7–8). Microscopic foci of stromal invasion were present, composed of nests of large polygonal cells with abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, well-defined borders, large pleomorphic nuclei, and areas of keratinization (Figures 9–10).

The remaining mesenchymal lesion showed alternating hypercellular and hypocellular areas composed of spindle cells with scant, ill-defined cytoplasm, nuclear enlargement, multifocal pleomorphism, open chromatin, and superficial necrosis (ulcerated zone), without mitoses.

Figure 7–8. Histologic sections of the transcervical lesion showing a mesenchymal neoplasm, with areas covered by high-grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia.

Figure 9-10. Microscopic foci of invasion into the stroma of the cervical lesion.

Histologic sections of the subserosal (bilobed) lesion demonstrated a mesenchymal neoplasm with fascicular growth patterns (long and short bundles), composed of spindle cells with blunt-ended nuclei, scant eosinophilic cytoplasm, nuclear enlargement, pleomorphism (Figure 11), multinucleation, and no mitoses. Areas of ischemic necrosis

(Figure 12) and edema were present. The endometrium showed irregular, non-complex glands lined by a single layer of columnar epithelium with apical vacuoles. The intramural lesion consisted of smooth muscle fibers with moderately eosinophilic cytoplasm, elongated blunt-ended nuclei with small nucleoli, without mitosis, necrosis, or atypia.

Figure 11-12. Histological sections of subserosal lesion, which present mesenchymal neoplasia with growth patterns in long and short bundles.

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The final histologic diagnosis was; Cervix with squamous cell carcinoma in situ; surgical margins not assessable. Transcervical tumor (10 × 9 × 6 cm): mesenchymal neoplasm consistent with symplastic leiomyoma in collision with squamous cell carcinoma in situ and microscopic foci of invasive squamous cell carcinoma. Bilobed subserosal tumor (18 × 11 × 7 cm): consistent with smooth muscle tumor of uncertain malignant potential (STUMP); requires staging work-up. Conventional-type intramural leiomyoma, 9 × 7.5 cm and a secretory endometrium.

The patient required intraoperative transfusion of two packed red blood cell units. She received postoperative antibiotic therapy with cefotaxime 1 g IV every 12 hours and analgesia with NSAIDs.

Postoperative monitoring continued for 2 days, during which she evolved satisfactorily, tolerating oral intake and ambulation, with progressive decrease in postoperative pain, normal urine output, and normoactive bowel sounds. Vital signs remained stable.

A control complete blood count on postoperative day 2 showed hemoglobin of 8.2g/dL, and the patient was discharged home. She presented to follow-up 10 days after discharge with adequate recovery. One-month follow-up at her primary care unit prompted referral to medical and surgical oncology due to the potential malignant behavior of the STUMP.

DISCUSSION

Our case describes a set of uterine neoplasms diagnosed after a total hysterectomy performed in a woman with excessive uterine bleeding leading to severe anemia. The patient's age did not correspond with what is typically expected for a smooth muscle tumor of uncertain malignant potential (STUMP), which is usually diagnosed around 45 years of age. (2)

The clinical characteristics were consistent with the typical presentation of a patient with leiomyomas, with excessive uterine bleeding and pelvic mass symptoms being the most prominent. (8) However, in the reviewed literature, the presence of a STUMP has not been associated with squamous cell carcinoma.

Imaging distinction between STUMP and leiomyosarcoma is virtually impossible. Due to their wide availability, these lesions are most commonly evaluated using ultrasonography. The most frequent ultrasonographic features associated with malignant potential include irregular lesion borders, irregular cystic areas, non-uniform echotexture, mixed echogenicity, and increased vascularization; however, none of these findings is specific for malignancy. Malignant lesions tend to be solitary, larger in size, and exhibit rapid growth. (9)

There is no consensus regarding the diagnostic criteria for STUMP. Clinically, the diagnosis is established when the Stanford criteria for leiomyosarcoma are not met, but certain

histologic features suggest malignant potential. The lesion must present one of the following three criteria: moderate to severe diffuse atypia, a mitotic index of at least 10 mitoses per 10 high-power fields, or tumor cell necrosis. In the discussed case, the mitotic index was below 10 mitoses per field, cellular atypia was mild, and the lesion did present tumor cell necrosis. (10) Had two or more criteria been met, the tumor would have been classified as a sarcoma.

The use of immunohistochemistry with antibody panels such as p16, p53, and Ki-67 poses a diagnostic challenge in these tumors. Ki-67 and p53 expression levels are significantly higher in leiomyosarcomas than in STUMPs, while p16 expression shows no significant difference between leiomyomas and STUMPs. Despite this, the immunohistochemical patterns of these markers do not provide sufficient discriminatory power to differentiate between leiomyomas and atypical leiomyomas. (11)

There are no established guidelines for the management of STUMP, but surgical treatment appears to be an appropriate first-line therapy, with the main challenge being the inability to plan management preoperatively. (2)

Unlike leiomyomas, STUMPs have a recurrence rate ranging from 8.7% to 11%. (7) This risk has been partly associated with statements by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) regarding the potential hazards of fibroid morcellation, since this practice may favor recurrence, either again as STUMP or as leiomyosarcoma. Reported recurrence intervals vary widely, from 2 to 194 months, and recurrences predominantly occur in the uterus, pelvis, lungs, retroperitoneum, liver, and bones. Notably, disease-free interval does not appear to correlate with the type of surgical approach (laparoscopy vs laparotomy) or histologic variants, but rather with a prior history of morcellation. (12)

Compared to other tumors, recurrence tends to be more unpredictable, as reported by Rizzo et al., who found a 33% rate of local recurrence, 33% pulmonary recurrence, and 15% osseous recurrence. (13) The histologic type in recurrent cases varies, with leiomyosarcoma being the most common, present in approximately 32% of cases, which consequently influences therapeutic options, ranging from surgical management to oncologic resection. Despite advances in the understanding of this pathology, risk factors for malignant degeneration have not been clearly identified. (14)

There is no standardized management for STUMPs or their recurrences. Since the pelvis is the most common site of recurrence, surgical management appears to be the first-line approach. In cases where surgery is not feasible, the most commonly used chemotherapeutic regimens mirror those used for leiomyosarcoma and include doxorubicin plus ifosfamide and gemcitabine plus docetaxel. Aromatase inhibitors and progesterone have also been used as treatment options. Radiotherapy is not indicated in the management of these tumors. (15)

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Despite these considerations, it is important to emphasize that these tumors generally carry a favorable prognosis, and surgical therapy is successful in most cases.

CONCLUSION

Smooth muscle tumors of uncertain malignant potential represent both a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge, primarily due to the inability to plan management prior to surgical intervention, as diagnosis is typically made after tumor resection. There is no consensus regarding treatment or patient follow-up, with recurrence risk being the main concern. Therefore, individualized management and close surveillance are essential for patients with these tumors.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This case report has been removed from all data related to the patient.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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